

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Strip cropping in practice: Higher slug abundance despite a higher number of slug-predating carabid species

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Abstract

1. Strip cropping involves growing multiple crops in adjacent strips in a field, which facilitates existing management routines while promoting ecological interactions. While strip cropping can promote in-field biodiversity and biological control of insect pests, it is unclear how strip cropping affects in-field slugs, which can cause considerable crop damage.
2. We selected 20 farms across the Netherlands with paired monoculture and strip cropping fields. The strip cropping fields varied in strip width (3–33 m), number of crop species grown (2–9 crops), and farming system (conventional or organic). We used a combination of shelter and pitfall traps to quantify populations of slugs and their arthropod predators in cereals.
3. Absolute slug abundance was low at most farms, but was 3–5 times higher in strip cropping relative to paired monocultures. Slug abundance in strip cropping increased with increasing strip width. Farming system, cereal type, soil type, or the number of crop species did not mediate the effect of strip cropping on slug abundances.
4. Natural enemy diversity was around 25% higher in strip cropping, and this effect of strip cropping was mediated by cereal type and soil type. Farming system, strip width, or number of crops did not mediate the effect of strip cropping on natural enemy diversity.
5. Most farmers reported similar levels of slug damage in cereals in strip cropping and monoculture. However, some farmers reported increased slug damage in other crops within the strip cropping arrangement, especially at farms with relatively high slug abundances.
6. *Synthesis and applications.* To avoid increased slug damage in strip cropping fields in slug-prone areas, potential slug-source crops should be spatially separated from slug-sensitive crops. However, an increase in slug abundance should not deter the adoption of strip cropping as higher slug damage in strip cropping systems was rarely observed by farmers.

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KEYWORDS

Carabidae, cereal, conservation biological control, crop diversification, ecological intensification, gastropod, intercropping, pest management

1 | INTRODUCTION

Strip cropping is a versatile form of crop diversification where crops are grown in relatively narrow strips, and the arrangement and diversity of crops can be adjusted to farm goals and available means. Strip cropping can reduce plant diseases (Homulle et al., 2024), reduce the abundance of and damage caused by herbivorous insects (Croijmans, Mertens, et al., 2025; Cuperus et al., 2023), increase the diversity and abundance of natural enemies (Croijmans et al., 2024; Croijmans, Cuperus, et al., 2025), and increase crop yield, although the effect on crop yield varies (Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023; Ditzler et al., 2023; Labrie et al., 2016; Thompson et al., 2025). Nevertheless, an organic strip cropping system has been found to increase revenue across all crops (Juventia & van Apeldoorn, 2024). However, most research on the effect of strip cropping on pest management has focused on arthropod pests (Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023; Lopes et al., 2016), despite the apparent economic importance and behavioural and physiological differences of some non-arthropod groups, like slugs (Douglas & Tooker, 2012; South, 1991).

Whereas strip cropping has been effective in reducing damage caused by diseases and herbivorous insects (Croijmans, Mertens, et al., 2025; Homulle et al., 2024), information on the effect of strip cropping on slugs is scarce and inconclusive (Tonhasca Jr. & Stinner, 1991). Growing crops with differing phenologies within a field may provide generalist slugs with a more continuous supply of food and shelter, potentially leading to greater slug abundance (South, 1991). Slugs thrive in low-disturbance areas and are vulnerable to tillage practices that often precede sowing or planting (Douglas & Tooker, 2012). Slugs overwinter mostly in field margins, which are often less disturbed and contain more vegetation early in the season, and colonize fields from there (Fusser et al., 2017). Relay strip cropping that includes both winter and spring crops might be beneficial to slugs, as winter crops could function as source habitats from which slugs can colonize adjacent spring crops soon after sowing or planting. Thus, strip cropping may reduce bottom-up control of slugs by creating a more favourable within-field habitat for overwintering, survival, and colonization.

A diverse community of natural enemies may reduce the risk of slug outbreaks. Several groups of arthropods, such as ground beetles and harvestmen, predate on slugs (Barker, 2004). However, many slugs grow large enough to deter attacks from smaller invertebrate predators (Barker, 2004). Invertebrate predators will usually prefer smaller slugs over larger ones and other prey over slugs (Symondson et al., 2006). Effective top-down control of slugs by arthropods thus requires a high abundance and functional diversity of predators capable of preying on them.

Strip cropping can increase richness and abundance of important slug predators (Alarcón-Segura et al., 2022; Croijmans, Cuperus, et al., 2025) and may therefore increase the probability of effective top-down suppression of slugs by these predators. It remains, however, unclear how the balance between potential bottom-up versus top-down forces on slugs in strip cropping systems unfolds on-farm.

Strip cropping entails a wide variety of combinations of crop species, strip widths, and management, which can influence the functioning of these systems. Many studies used strip widths of 3m or below (e.g. Cuperus et al., 2023; Homulle et al., 2024), but some used wide strips of 12m or more (Alarcón-Segura et al., 2022; Labrie et al., 2016; Thompson et al., 2025). To the best of our knowledge, only one study examined the effect of strip width on pest control potential, but this study only comprised one geographical location (Cuperus et al., 2024). Wider strips increased spider abundances but lowered rove beetle abundances, while ground beetle abundance and diversity showed variable responses (Cuperus et al., 2024). Moreover, most studies only examined strip cropping with a fixed number of crop species within their strip cropping arrangement (e.g. Homulle et al., 2024; Juventia & van Apeldoorn, 2024; Labrie et al., 2016). Only a few studies examined the effect of increasing the number of crop species in the strip cropping arrangement (e.g. Ditzler et al., 2021; Karssemeijer et al., 2024). These studies observed limited effects of increasing crop diversity on pests and their natural enemies, but the generalizability of these results is unclear as these studies were all from a single location in the Netherlands. Therefore, there is still limited understanding of how specific characteristics of strip cropping systems influence pest management.

Here we investigated how strip cropping alters slug populations and their ground-dwelling arthropod natural enemies, and how characteristics of the strip cropping system influence the effect of strip cropping. We observed slugs and their predators on 20 independent farms across the Netherlands that had both a strip-cropped field that included cereal and a monoculture cereal field. We formulated three research questions. (1) Does strip cropping affect the abundance of slugs and their natural enemy abundance and diversity? (2) Does the effect of strip cropping on slugs and their natural enemies depend on the farming system (conventional or organic), cereal type (winter- or spring-sown), soil type (clay or sand), strip width, and the number of crop species in the strip cropping arrangement? (3) Do farmers perceive an effect of strip cropping on slug damage to crops? As it is often complicated to link changes in herbivore abundances to losses in marketable yield (Croijmans, Mertens, et al., 2025), we asked farmers to report whether the difference in slug abundance between strip crops and monoculture fields translated to relevant changes in crop injury and yield.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study area and field design

In the Netherlands, more than 120 fields were strip-cropped in 2023 (Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland, 2024), which provided the unique opportunity to assess the effect of strip cropping on pest management across a wide variety of strip cropping arrangements in realistic on-farm settings. For this study, we selected all 20 farms that had both a field with a strip-cropped cereal and a matching field with the same cereal species grown as a monoculture under similar management (Figure 1, Table 1). We use the term 'monoculture' to refer to fields with a single crop species, rather than the continuous cultivation of the same crop species in a field in subsequent years. At four farms, we made observations in two distinct strip cropping designs, while a single monoculture field was used as a reference on those farms (Table 1). Per farm, the strip-cropped and monoculture fields were under the same farming system (organic or conventional), and the same crop species and type (winter- or spring-sown) were grown (with few exceptions; see Table S1).

We aimed to obtain fields that represented a wide variation of farming systems, strip widths, and number of different crops, with minimal confounding between these factors. There was, however, some confounding between farming system and strip width because strip width on organic farms varied between 3 and 12 m, with one exception of 24 m, while on conventional farms strip width ranged more widely, from 3 to 33 m. The focal cereal species in which the observations were made were winter or spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), winter or spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) or spring oat (*Avena sativa*). The study was conducted in 2024. This year had a relatively wet spring which provided favourable conditions for slugs (Siegmund, 2024). None of the farmers used chemical or biological molluscicides or targeted mechanical measures to combat slugs throughout the growth of the cereals.

2.2 | Shelter traps

We used shelter traps to assess slug abundance (Douglas & Tooker, 2012; Figure S1a,b). These traps consisted of 20 × 30 cm

FIGURE 1 Location of farms and sampling design. (a) Location of twenty sampled farms across the Netherlands. On each farm observations were made in a monoculture cereal crop and in one (or two) strip-cropped field(s) comprising the same cereal under the same management as the monoculture. (b) Spatial design of sample locations for sets of shelter and pitfall traps (blue circles). Within one sample location a set of one shelter and one pitfall trap were placed. Six of each type of trap were placed in monoculture fields and 12 in strip crop fields (six 30 cm from the edge of the strip, six in the middle of the strip). Two sets of traps in each sample location are highlighted in the figure. When multiple strips with the same cereal were available, we sampled in up to three different strips. When we sampled in three strips, we placed two sets of traps per strip (pink circles); with two strips, we placed three sets per strip; and with one strip, we placed all six sets in this strip (purple hexagons). The spatial arrangement of the traps in the monoculture was the same as the middle samples in the strip-cropped field. Traps were placed 15–50 m from the field edge, depending on the length of the strip-cropped field. The distance from the edge was the same per paired monoculture and strip-cropped field.

TABLE 1 Attributes of 24 strip-cropped fields, and their associated monoculture fields, on 20 farms.

Farm code (+ .field)	Soil type	Farming system	Winter- or spring-sown	Cereal species	Strip width (m)	Crop diversity	Start strip cropping	Monoculture size (m)
F01	Clay	Conventional	Winter	Wheat	9	9	2021	80×280
F02	Sand	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	15	8	2019	60×400
F03.1	Clay	Organic	Spring	Oat	3	6	2023	80×65
F03.2	Clay	Organic	Spring	Oat	3	2	2023	80×65
F04.1	Clay	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	3	6	2022	240×1000
F04.2	Clay	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	15	2	2022	240×1000
F05	Sand	Conventional	Winter	Barley	6	9	2020	120×450
F06.1	Sand	Organic	Spring	Oat	3	6	2019	70×65
F06.2	Sand	Organic	Spring	Oat	3	2	2021	70×65
F07	Clay	Organic	Spring	Oat	6	9	2020	90×250
F08	Sand	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	21	7	2023	110×600
F09	Clay	Conventional	Winter	Wheat	24	5	2021	120×230
F10	Sand	Conventional	Winter	Wheat	6	3	2020	120×200
F11	Sand	Conventional	Spring	Barley	12	5	2021	75×480
F12	Clay	Organic	Spring	Wheat	24	9	2020	140×460
F13	Clay	Conventional	Spring	Barley	33	4	2018	150×400
F14	Clay	Conventional	Winter	Wheat	33	5	2021	250×380
F15.1	Clay	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	6	6	2020	120×400
F15.2	Clay	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	12	6	2020	120×400
F16	Clay	Organic	Winter	Wheat	6	2	2020	155×245
F17	Sand	Conventional	Spring	Wheat	26	4	2024	360×580
F18	Clay	Conventional	Winter	Wheat	22	2	2024	140×400
F19	Sand	Conventional	Spring	Barley	6	4	2020	75×300
F20	Sand	Organic	Spring	Wheat	12	3	2020	140×230

Note: Sixteen farms had one strip-cropped and one monoculture field with the same cereal species. Four farms had two strip-cropped fields (e.g. F04.1 and F04.2) and one monoculture field with the same cereal species. Fourteen farms (16 strip-cropped fields + 14 monoculture fields) were conventionally managed, and six farms (eight strip-cropped fields + six monoculture fields) were organically managed. All fields on the same farm had the same soil type. Crop diversity indicates the number of distinct crop species used in the strip cropping arrangement. Start strip cropping is the year that strip cropping started on the strip-cropped field.

flat, dark-grey stone roof shingles. The shingles would leave some space on the slightly uneven soil, which would stay more humid and serve as a shelter for slugs during the day. The shelter traps were left in the field for 7 days, after which they were lifted and slugs underneath the shingle were identified to species and counted (Rowson et al., 2014). We performed a pilot experiment to assess whether heating of the shingle by sunlight and the colour of the shingle (white or dark grey) affected the abundance of slugs (Text S1). We did not find any difference in slug abundance between shingles with different colours or exposure to the sun.

2.3 | Pitfall traps

We used pitfall traps to assess the abundance and diversity of ground-dwelling arthropod natural enemies of slugs (Figure S1c). Pitfall traps consisted of a transparent plastic cup (5.9 cm bottom

diameter, 9.2 cm top diameter, 13.5 cm height) placed in the soil, so the top of the cup was level with the soil surface. We did not use funnels inside the cups. Pitfalls were filled with approximately 100 mL water mixed with non-perfumed soap (approximately 3 cm high water level) and covered with a black plastic rain cover (12.5 cm diameter) around 3 cm above the soil surface. Pitfall traps were left for 7 days, after which their contents were collected and stored in 70% ethanol. Ground beetles (Carabidae) were identified to species (Mulwijk et al., 2015). All other beetles (Coleoptera), true bugs (Heteroptera), and spiders (Araneae) were identified to family (Krediet et al., 2022). All other arthropods were identified to order.

2.4 | Sampling design

All samples were taken in two rounds in the meteorological spring (20 March–20 June) of 2024. The timing of sampling was based on

crop phenology and logistics. Sampling during the first round lasted from 3 April to 6 June, which coincided with the formation of the first three leaves of the spring cereals and a relatively dense cover for the winter cereals. This round spanned over 2 months as there were large differences in sowing date between farms. The second round lasted from 13 May to 14 June, when the spring cereals already had a denser cover and the difference between the cover of the winter and spring cereals largely disappeared. The farm visits of the second round were conducted at least 2 weeks and usually about 4 weeks after the first farm visit.

Per farm, we placed six sets of traps (shelter and pitfall) in the monoculture field and 12 sets in the strip-cropped field(s). For the strip-cropped fields, six sets of traps were placed in the middle of the strips (strip middle) and six sets 30 cm from the edge of the strips (strip edge), divided over both sides of the strip (left and right) (Figure 1b, Table S2). We will use “field position” to indicate the three different positions that traps were placed in: monoculture, strip middle, and strip edge. Traps in the strip cropping field were divided over one to three strips, depending on the availability of suitable strips with the same cereal. When three strips were sampled, we placed two sets of traps per strip; when two strips were sampled, we placed three sets per strip; when one strip was sampled, all traps were placed in that strip. Traps in the monoculture were placed in a similar spatial configuration as the traps in the middle of the corresponding strip-cropped field. To avoid effects of field margins, traps closest to the field margin were placed 15–50 m from the field margin, depending on the length of the strips. In the monoculture, we used the same distances from the field margin as in the strip-cropped field. The distance between traps in the middle of the same strip was 30 m. The distance between the edge and middle traps was at least 15 m. Shelter and pitfall traps were placed within 1 m from each other (Figure S1a), and at the exact same locations in both rounds. See Text S2 for any deviations in the sampling design and Croijmans et al. (2026) for the field map and sampling design per farm.

2.5 | Natural enemies of slugs

We extensively searched the literature for evidence of predation on live slugs by ground-dwelling arthropods caught in our pitfall traps (see details in Tables S3 and S4, Text S3). Based on the collected evidence, five groups of ground-dwelling arthropods kill slugs: centipedes (Chilopoda), harvestmen (Opiliones), large rove beetles (Staphylinidae), carrion beetles (Silphidae) of the subfamily Silphinae, and ground beetles (Carabidae) (Barker, 2004). The counts of individuals in these groups were used to calculate predator abundance and diversity. For our calculation of natural enemy richness, we included Carabidae mostly at the species level, Silphinae and Staphylinidae at (sub-)family level, and Chilopoda and Opiliones at order level (see details in Text S3).

2.6 | Body-mass-weighted abundance and effective number of slug-predating carabids

We calculated body mass-weighted measures of abundance (B) and effective number (e^H) of slug-predating carabid species to assess the overall slug predation pressure of the carabid community and its redundancy for the function of slug predation (Daouti et al., 2024). The body mass-weighted abundance is a measure for the total mass of slug eating carabids in the field, while the effective number represents the redundancy in predation by carabids, that is the extent to which having multiple species predating on slugs reduces the impact on predation if one of those species is lost (Daouti et al., 2024). We only include ground beetles in these analyses as we had accurate data on average body mass per species only for this group (Booij et al., 1994; Table S5). We only included ground beetles that are known as slug predators (Barker, 2004). The underlying principle for weighting by individual carabid body mass is that larger carabids eat more prey and hence contribute more to the predation pressure and to the effective number of species contributing to predation (Daouti et al., 2024). See Text S4 for the corresponding formulas.

2.7 | Data analysis

We conducted two sets of analyses, corresponding to research questions one (effect of strip cropping) and two (effect of covariables on the effect of strip cropping), using R version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022). The data from three farms (F11, F17, F19) without any slugs were excluded from all analyses because the absence of any slug prevented doing a meaningful analysis on the preference of slugs for strip-cropped or monoculture fields on these three farms (Table S2; Bolker, 2008). In the analyses, we were interested in comparing the number of slugs and slug predators in monoculture fields and strip-cropped fields and within the strip-cropped fields we were interested in comparing the middle of the strip and the strip edge. Hence, we compared the abundance of slugs, natural enemies, and body-mass-weighted abundance (B) and effective number of species (e^H) at three field positions: monoculture, strip middle, and strip edge. We summed the catches of the six shelter or pitfall traps for each field position (monoculture, strip middle, strip edge) per farm per round. When individual traps were destroyed or otherwise lost, these and an equal number of sub-samples in other field positions were discarded from the sum of the traps (Table S2). We fitted linear (mixed) models using the “glmmTMB” package (Brooks et al., 2017). All graphs were made using the “ggplot2” package (Wickham & Chang, 2016).

First, to analyse the overall effect of strip cropping, we used models for counts of slugs and natural enemies and body-mass-weighted metrics. We used a negative binomial distribution for slug and total natural enemy counts, normal distribution for natural enemy richness (taxa count), and gamma distribution with a log link function for body-mass-weighted abundance and effective

number of slug-predating carabids. In all models, we included field position (monoculture, strip middle or strip edge) as covariable. To account for spatial and temporal dependencies, we included farm and round as random effects, with round nested in farm such that every combination of round and farm was seen as an independent cluster (1|Farm:Round). We then tested all models for zero-inflation, and all models with a distribution for normality of residuals and homoscedasticity using the “DHARMA” package (Hartig, 2018). Then we tested whether field position significantly affected the dependent variables using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the “car” package (Fox et al., 2012). When the field position significantly influenced a dependent variable, we used estimated marginal means (EMM) to compare the levels of field positions using the “emmeans” (Lenth, 2018) and “multcomp” packages (Hothorn et al., 2016). In the post hoc analyses we corrected for multiple testing using Tukey’s HSD.

Second, to assess whether farming system, cereal type, soil type, strip width, and the number of crops mediated the effect of strip cropping, we standardized the dependent variables per farm and round. This standardization was necessary because farms and rounds differed markedly in absolute values, whereas our focus was on relative changes associated with strip cropping and farm characteristics. Therefore, we standardized the slug and natural enemy variables within a farm and round using z-scores:

$$z_{ij} = \frac{(x_{ij} - \mu_i)}{\sigma_i}$$

where x is the value of the dependent variable, μ is the average of the dependent variable and σ the standard deviation of the i th combination of farm and round (Farm:Round) and the j th field position (monoculture, strip middle, strip edge). These z-scores were calculated based on the sum of the six sub-samples per field position per farm per round, thus resulting in one z-score per field position per farm per round. We then calculated the differences between the field positions and fitted linear models with the difference between the monoculture and middle of strips and the difference between the middle and edge of strips as dependent variables. We used farming system, cereal type, soil type, strip width, and number of crop species as independent variables in an initial model. Then we performed model selection with AIC to select the most relevant cropping system characteristics for each slug and natural enemy variable, using the “MuMIn” package (Barton, 2025). We used normal distributions and tested for normality and homoscedasticity. ANOVA was used to assess whether included variables significantly affected the difference between monoculture and strip middle or strip middle and strip edge.

2.8 | Farmer interviews

To link our findings on slug abundances to crop damage, we asked all farmers about their experience with slug damage and management

in strip cropping (Text S5). We asked farmers: (1) whether they observed differences in slug damage between the cereals grown in strip cropping or monocultures, and if so, in which cropping system slug damage was higher; and (2) whether they observed relevant slug damage in other crops within the strip cropping arrangement. The results of the farmer interviews were not quantitatively analysed.

2.9 | Ethics approval and permissions

Our field research was not reviewed by an institutional or governmental regulatory body as the work was performed on invertebrates. All farmers gave verbal or written informed consent for access to their lands and to carry out our measurements. We have received written informed consent from farmers for publication of the anonymized data and results, and for participation in interviews regarding slug damage and management.

3 | RESULTS

We observed 529 slugs belonging to seven species, and we found no slugs under 657 out of 816 shelter traps. *Deroceras reticulatum* (45% of all slugs) and *Arion vulgaris* (42%) were the most common species across all farms, both of which are known as pests of agricultural crops (Rowson et al., 2014). *Limax maximus* and *Arion circumscriptus* were common at specific farms. Across the 17 included farms, we observed 20,679 natural enemies of slugs belonging to 23 taxa. Carabidae (92%) were by far the most numerous group. *Poecilus cupreus* (39%), *Pterostichus melanarius* (30%), *Anchomenus dorsalis* (9.6%), and *Harpalus rufipes* (6.5%) were the most common potentially slug-predating Carabidae.

3.1 | Overall effect of strip cropping on slugs and their natural enemies

We found on average 0.46 (SE: 0.19) slugs per six shelter traps in the monocultures, whereas slug abundances were significantly higher in the middle (1.69 slugs, SE: 0.59) and edge of strips (2.42 slugs, SE: 0.83) (Figure 2). Slug abundances were not significantly different between strip edge and middle (Figure 2).

Both the abundance of all slug natural enemies and the body-mass-weighted abundance of slug-predating carabids were about 60% higher in the edges of strips in strip-cropped fields than in the monoculture fields, but they did not significantly differ between the middle of strips and monocultures (Figure 3A,C). Slug natural enemy richness and the effective number of slug-predating carabid species (e^H) were around 25% higher in strip cropping than in monocultures (Figure 3B,D). For all natural enemy metrics, the middle of strip cropping did not significantly differ from the edge (Figure 3).

FIGURE 2 Effect of cropping system on slug abundance. Slug abundance was measured using shelter traps in cereals in monocultures ($n=34$), or at the middle ($n=42$) or edge of strips ($n=42$). Squares with lines show model-estimated means $\pm 95\%$ CIs; compact letter display marks significant differences. Jittered points represent abundance per six shelter traps in a field position per farm per round. Arrows with numbers on top indicate outliers, with the numbers indicating the number of outliers. Outliers were included in the analysis.

3.2 | Factors influencing the effect of strip cropping on slugs and their natural enemies

The difference between strip middle and monoculture was negatively correlated with strip width, indicating that slug abundance is higher in the middle of wider strips than in the middle of narrower strips (Figure 4). However, the difference between the middle and edge of strips was not affected by strip width (Figure S2). The effect of strip cropping on slug abundance was not affected by farming system (conventional or organic), cereal type (winter- or spring-sown), soil type (clay or sand), or number of crop species in the strip cropping arrangement.

We found strong evidence that cereal type ($p < 0.001$) and soil type ($p = 0.002$), and weak evidence that the number of crops ($p = 0.058$) influenced the effect of strip cropping on natural enemy richness (Figure 4). In winter cereals and on sandy soils, the natural enemy richness was higher in strip cropping than in monocultures, whereas in spring cereals and on clay soils we found no difference. The difference in natural enemy richness between strip cropping and monocultures was greater when strip crops comprised fewer species. Moreover, we observed a greater difference in natural enemy richness between the edges and middle of the strips when strips were wider ($p = 0.013$; Figure S2). We found weak evidence that cereal type ($p = 0.075$) influenced the effect of strip cropping on the effective number of slug-predating carabid species (e^H), where e^H was higher in strip-cropped winter cereals compared with monocultures, but not in spring cereals (Figure 4). Moreover, we found moderate evidence that e^H was higher in the edges compared with the middle of strips at conventional farms, but not at organic farms ($p = 0.040$; Figure S2). The effect of strip cropping on natural enemy abundance and body-mass-weighted carabid abundance (B) was not affected by any of the strip cropping characteristics (Figure 4).

3.3 | Farmer perceptions on slug damage

None of the farmers reported a difference in slug damage between cereals grown in strip cropping or monocultures, except for one farmer who observed slightly more slug damage in strip-cropped cereals (Table S8). Four farmers mentioned damage in other crops within the strip cropping arrangement, including soybean (*Glycine max*), white cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*), sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*), chicory (*Cichorium intybus*), and pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*) (Table S8). Three of these four farmers had the highest slug abundances among all farms.

4 | DISCUSSION

Both slug abundance and the abundance and diversity of their natural enemies were higher in strip-cropped cereals compared with cereal monocultures. Slug abundances were 3.5–5 times higher in strip cropping, and these effects were mostly consistent across strip cropping characteristics. However, slug abundances were positively related to strip width. Natural enemy abundance and body-mass-weighted abundance of slug-predating carabids were not influenced by any of the strip-cropping characteristics, while natural enemy diversity (natural enemy richness and effective number of slug-predating carabids) was influenced by cereal type, soil type, and number of crops. Thus, our results indicate that strip cropping greatly reduced bottom-up control of slugs, facilitating higher densities of slugs, while it led to relatively small increases in potential top-down control. Nevertheless, overall slug abundances were low

FIGURE 3 Effect of cropping system on natural enemy variables: (A) total natural enemy abundance (individuals per six pitfall traps), (B) total natural enemy richness (species per six pitfall traps), (C) body-mass-weighted slug-predating carabid abundance (mg predator mass per six pitfall traps), and (D) effective number of slug-predating carabids. Natural enemies in cereals were analysed using sums of six pitfall traps in monocultures ($n=34$), or at the middle ($n=42$) or edge of strips ($n=42$). Squares with lines show model-estimated means $\pm 95\%$ CIs; compact letter display marks significant differences. Jittered points represent raw data. Arrows with numbers on top indicate outliers, with the numbers indicating the number of outliers. Outliers were included in the analysis.

at 16 out of 20 farms, and nearly all farmers observed similar (low) slug damage between cereals grown in strip cropping or monocultures. Thus, despite marked increases in slug abundances through strip cropping, strip cropping did not lead to reported slug problems in cereals.

The higher slug density in strip cropping shows stark contrast with existing literature on the effects of intercropping on herbivorous arthropods. Several meta-analyses show that intercropping and increasing crop diversity reduce the abundance of herbivorous arthropods (Hahn & Cammarano, 2023; Lopes et al., 2016; Yousefi et al., 2024), whereas the only previous study on the effect of

intercropping on slug abundances showed no effect (Tonhasca Jr. & Stinner, 1991). Our findings indicate that slugs are uniquely affected by strip- or intercropping compared with arthropod herbivores. The abundance of insects with a relatively narrow diet breadth, like cereal aphids or rape pollen beetles, might be reduced in strip cropping (Alarcón-Segura et al., 2022; Labrie et al., 2016) due to other crops serving as a non-host barrier (Yousefi et al., 2024). Yet, for highly generalist organisms, like many slug species, strip cropping might provide more consistent food sources or shelter. Thus, strip cropping appears to reduce bottom-up control of slugs by providing a more diverse and therefore more conducive habitat.

FIGURE 4 Summary of effects of strip-cropping characteristics on the difference between monoculture and strip cropping for slugs and their natural enemies. The rows indicate the overall effect of strip cropping and the mediating effects of strip cropping characteristics (farming system, cereal type, soil type, strip width, and number of crops). The columns indicate the different slug and natural enemy variables (slug abundance, natural enemy abundance and richness, body-mass-weighted abundance (B) and effective number of slug-predating carabids (e^H)). “+” indicates that the difference between monoculture and strip edge was significant, but between monoculture and strip middle not. Figures corresponding to mediating effects and model output can be found in the Appendix (Figures S3–S5, Table S6).

While strip cropping supported more natural enemies than monocultures, predation levels were not sufficient to exert meaningful top-down control of slugs in strip cropping systems. The natural enemies that we found are mostly generalist omnivores that

can also feed on a diversity of other invertebrates and weed seeds (Daouti et al., 2024; Guenay-Greunke et al., 2024). As strip cropping has been shown to increase weed and insect abundances (Croijmans, Mertens, et al., 2025; Ditzler et al., 2023), natural enemies could

have switched to alternative prey in strip-cropped fields. In contrast to arthropod pests, slugs mostly benefit from strip cropping due to reduced bottom-up control, while the limited increase in potential top-down control in strip cropping is not sufficient for an effective reduction of slug abundance.

The increase of slugs and their natural enemies in strip cropping might be explained by a reduction in colonization distance. Field margins are known to be source habitats for both slugs and natural enemies, and their abundance and diversity diminish with increasing distance from field edges (Fusser et al., 2017; Hof & Bright, 2010). Strip cropping facilitates colonization by combining multiple habitats within a field, especially when potential source habitats are included, such as beetle banks, flower strips or perennial crops (Bianchi et al., 2006). The relatively small plot sizes (strips) in strip cropping systems lead to relatively short distance between source habitats and the crop, which facilitates crop colonization of both slugs and their natural enemies (Petit et al., 2023).

Cereal type and soil type were important moderators of the positive effect of strip cropping on natural enemy diversity. Winter cereals create a stable overwintering habitat, especially in strip cropping, where adjacent strips regularly remained barren throughout the winter. Spring cereals, on the other hand, are sown in the spring, thus creating a less-contrasting habitat to other, later-planted crops in strip cropping. Therefore, natural enemies might aggregate more in winter cereal strips, whereas they are more homogeneously distributed in strip cropping systems with spring cereals (Wan et al., 2018). The farms on clay soils were mostly in polders that are reclaimed from the sea. In these polders, Carabid communities are often dominated by *Pterostichus melanarius* and *Poecilus cupreus*. Farms on sandy soils were regularly located in more diverse landscapes and usually had more species-rich natural enemy communities with greater evenness of species abundances (Croijmans, Cuperus, et al., 2025). The effect of soil type on strip cropping might thus be a combination of soil-mediated and landscape-mediated effects, resulting in strip-cropped fields on sandy soils having relatively richer natural enemy communities, as they have larger communities of natural enemies to draw from within the landscape (Tschartke et al., 2012).

We used z-scores to assess the effect of strip cropping and farm characteristics on the relative abundance of slugs and their predators at three field positions: in monoculture fields and in the strip-cropped fields in the middle or at the edge of the strips. Z-scores standardize the values per farm, such that the difference between field positions on different farms is independent of whether slug counts are high or low, that is they are measured at the same scale, irrespective of abundance. This differs from the overall analysis comparing the abundance values at the three field positions, in which the data on the original scale of measurement were used. The use of z-scores puts random variation on farms with low counts on the same scale as more reliable differences between field positions on farms with high counts. This effect of using z-scores, while necessary to do the analysis at all, may have affected the power to detect effects of farm variables on the relative abundance at the three field positions, and it could also be the reason for finding some

counter-intuitive results. For example, our analysis showed a larger relative difference between monocultures and the middle of strips in strip-cropped fields with wider strips, despite wider strips being more akin to monocultures (Van Oort et al., 2020). Although we have strong evidence for an overall increase in slug abundance in strip cropping, using analyses with unstandardized data, we have limited evidence for the presence or absence of any mediating effects of strip cropping and farm characteristics (including strip width).

Strip cropping enhanced slug abundance, but still slugs were only problematic at a few farms. Farmers did not report major slug damage in cereals, although in some cases other crops showed major slug damage. Similarly, strip cropping was found to increase insect herbivore abundances, but these larger population sizes in strip cropping did not translate to higher yield losses or damage (Croijmans, Mertens, et al., 2025). An important consideration is that cereals in strip cropping might serve as a source of slugs, from which slugs may colonize slug-sensitive crops. Combining winter crops with spring-sown companion crops in a relay strip crop might be particularly problematic, as this would facilitate the movement of slugs from the winter cereal to the seedlings of the spring crop at the seedling stage, when the plants are very palatable to slugs. In a previous study, crop compatibility was used to design strip cropping arrangements, yet crop species compatibility did not consider slug pressure (Juventia et al., 2022). The most important strip cropping design consideration to avoid slug damage is to spatially separate winter cereals from slug-sensitive crops, like cabbage or beans.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

All in all, our findings did not align with our expectations. We expected that a diversified crop system, like strip cropping, would result in higher abundance and diversity of slug natural enemies, enhanced slug predation, and reduced slug abundance and crop damage. Our results show that natural enemy densities were somewhat increased, while slug densities increased 3.5–5-fold. Hence, crop system diversification had a greater favourable effect on slugs than on their natural enemies. Nevertheless, slug densities and slug damage were relatively low at most of the studied farms. Farmers indicated that slugs did not pose a problem in cereals, but occasionally in certain companion crops. We conclude that slugs are not an insurmountable problem in strip cropping, but our expectation that strip cropping would suppress slugs was not supported by our data.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Luuk Croijmans: Conceptualization, methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing, visualization, supervision. **Rik Waenink:** Conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing—review and editing, supervision. **Hilde Faber:** Conceptualization, investigation, writing—review and editing. **Wopke van der Werf:** Formal analysis, writing—review and editing, funding acquisition. **Berend de Jonge:** Methodology, validation, investigation. **Roos Lenders:** Formal

analysis, investigation. **Nienke Lekkerkerk**: Investigation. **Merel A. J. Hofmeijer**: Conceptualization, writing—review and editing. **Felix J. J. A. Bianchi**: Conceptualization, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this article.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and scripts are publicly available from 4TU.ResearchData via the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4121/f7553b0c-620b-4a79-a3bf-5646117d5b7a> (Croijmans et al., 2026).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Figure S1. Shelter trap and pitfall trap set-ups in the field.

Figure S2. Summary of effects of strip cropping characteristics on the difference between strip middle and edge for slugs and their natural enemies.

Figure S3. The effect of strip cropping characteristics on slug abundance.

Figure S4. The effect of strip cropping characteristics on natural enemy richness.

Figure S5. The effect of strip cropping characteristics on the effective number of slug-predating carabid species.

Table S1. Differences in crop management between monoculture and strip cropping per farm.

Table S2. Replication overview and hierarchy.

Table S3. Ground-dwelling arthropods found in pitfall traps and their capacity to kill slugs.

Table S4. Carabid species found in pitfall traps and their capacity to kill slugs.

Table S5. Body masses of individual slug-predating carabid beetles (Mi).

Table S6. Model output for the effect of strip cropping characteristics on the difference between monoculture and strip middle.

Table S7. Model output for the effect of strip cropping characteristics on the difference between strip middle and strip edge.

Table S8. Farmer perceptions on slug damage.

Appendix Text S1. Pilot shelter trap colour and sampling time.

Appendix Text S2. Deviations from sampling scheme.

Appendix Text S3. Justification decision on slug-predating arthropods caught in pitfall traps.

Appendix Text S4. Formulas and justification of body-mass weighted abundance and effective number of slug-predating carabids.

Appendix Text S5. Standard interview questions for farmer perspectives on slug management and damage.

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